

EBITDA AS A TOOL FOR ASSESSING BUSINESS OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN ECONOMIC INSTABILITY

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Abstract

This article examines EBITDA as a tool for assessing the operational efficiency (OE) of a business in conditions of economic instability. The article examines how it helps to identify the stability of the business model to external factors, including inflation, crises and market fluctuations. The theoretical aspects of EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization), its structure and advantages are analyzed. The role of this indicator in comparative analysis is evaluated, which allows investors and analysts to identify companies with high OE, as well as the ability of businesses to adapt to changing economic conditions. Using the example of companies, it is shown how EBITDA contributes to maintaining sustainability and risk management.

Keywords: operational efficiency (OE), EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization), economic instability, business resilience, investment analysis, operating expenses.

Introduction

In the context of global economic instability, driven by factors such as pandemics, geopolitical conflicts, changes in international trade agreements, and inflationary risks, companies face the need to optimize their operational processes and assess their resilience. One of the key indicators reflecting a business's operational efficiency (OE) is EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization). This metric allows for the assessment of a company's «pure» operational activity, which is especially critical during crisis periods when external conditions are unpredictable and frequently shift.

The relevance of this topic is underscored by the necessity to develop approaches for assessing the OE

of companies, the resilience of their business models, and their ability to handle economic challenges. Despite certain limitations, EBITDA has gained particular importance for evaluating OE and business survival in a turbulent economic environment. The objective of this research is to explore the potential of EBITDA as a tool for assessing the OE of businesses under economic instability.

Main part. Theoretical foundations of EBITDA

Indicator EBITDA is one of the most versatile tools for analyzing a company's OE. It reflects the company's profit before deductions for interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Calculation of the EBITDA indicator formula [1]

The elements of EBITDA consist of multiple crucial parts, and omitting these enables emphasis on the company's OE. **Net income** indicates the ultimate profit following all subtractions, including taxes, interest, and depreciation, and acts as the foundation for the initial approach to calculating this indicator. **Interest expenses**, or costs related to servicing debt, are omitted to eliminate the impact of the company's capital structure on the metric. **Taxes**, being compulsory payments to the government, are likewise omitted, which standardizes the measure and renders it independent of the tax systems of various nations and areas.

The alternative approach to calculating EBITDA relies on operating profit, which is profit excluding interest and tax deductions yet includes depreciation

costs. **Depreciation** signifies the deterioration of physical assets, including machinery, buildings, and equipment. Omitting depreciation enables the evaluation of a firm's operating profit without factoring in the capital intensity of the enterprise, which is especially crucial for businesses with significant capital investments. **The amortization process** for intangible assets resembles depreciation, but it is specifically related to non-physical assets like patents and licenses [2]. The addition of amortization allows for a more standardized comparison among companies that possess different intangible assets. All these components perform an important function in calculating this indicator, excluding aspects unrelated to operational activities and offering a more transparent view of the company's ability to generate profit.

Using EBITDA provides many advantages, which makes it an important business assessment tool. Since it does not include taxes, interest and depreciation, it allows you to objectively assess the operating profit of a company, regardless of its capital structure and tax strategies. This makes it especially useful for evaluating companies in different countries and sectors where financial and tax laws may differ significantly.

Using this indicator, investors and analysts can evaluate companies with different capital structures and depreciation levels, which makes it useful for comparative analysis. For example, in industries requiring significant capital and with high depreciation costs, this indicator provides a broader picture of the profitability of production. Excluding depreciation and interest expense, EBITDA provides a rough estimate of operating cash flow, which helps to assess how effectively a company generates cash to cover its current expenses. Although this indicator is not directly related to cash flow, it is often used to assess a company's ability to finance its operations without taking into account temporary factors related to depreciation and taxes.

In investment analysis, EBITDA is often used as multiples, such as EV/EBITDA, where the enterprise value (EV) is divided by EBITDA. This ratio helps investors **assess how profitable a company is compared to similar companies in the market**. This indicator is relatively easy to calculate and is widely used in financial statements and analytical reports. Thus, this indicator is an important tool for evaluating the effectiveness of a business and its ability to generate profit regardless of financial and tax factors.

Analysis of EBITDA as an indicator of OE

The EBITDA metric serves as an essential indicator for assessing the resilience of a company's operating model, as it reflects the profit generated from core activities while excluding factors unrelated to operational processes. Operational model resilience implies a company's ability to sustain and develop its processes consistently, generating sufficient profit to cover current expenses and reinvest in growth, despite shifts in the economic environment. Indicator EBITDA allows for the assessment of this resilience, as it reveals the strength and stability of a company's operating flows, independent of its capital structure and tax environment.

The principles of using EBITDA to analyze resilience can be viewed as a comprehensive approach to assessing a business's OE in changing conditions. First

and foremost, it focuses on pure operating profit, making it an accurate indicator of income generated directly from the company's core activities. A high and stable level confirms the business's ability to consistently earn profit from its operations. For investors and analysts, this is a crucial signal, especially in an unstable economy where external factors can distort other indicators. In such cases, EBITDA demonstrates how effectively a company manages its internal processes, costs, and revenues related to core operations.

Furthermore, EBITDA often serves as the **basis for comparative analysis of operational resilience** both within and across industries. Companies showing a higher level of this metric compared to competitors gain an advantage through efficient operational cost management and adaptability to changes in the economic environment. This advantage becomes especially significant for capital-intensive industries, such as energy and manufacturing, where depreciation expenses can heavily impact financial results. EBITDA allows for the evaluation of companies' true OE without accounting for these capital-intensive factors, creating a more transparent financial picture.

An essential part of the analysis is the **trend in EBITDA over time**, which also indicates the long-term sustainability of the business model. If the metric declines, this may indicate issues with cost management, reduced product demand, or the impact of adverse economic factors on operations. Conversely, a stable or growing value indicates the presence of a stable business model capable of adapting to external changes and maintaining OE.

Finally, a stable and high EBITDA level indicates the company's **financial flexibility**, which becomes vital in economically unstable conditions. The ability to generate steady cash flow provides resources for debt servicing, growth investments, and covering operating expenses, making the company more resilient to crises. Companies with high indicator levels can reinvest profits, attract additional funds, and maintain a stable market position. Such flexibility is particularly important for businesses operating under volatile demand and intense competition, where the stability of operational profit is critical for survival.

Indicator EBITDA also aids in **managing operational risks**, as it allows for a rapid assessment of how vulnerable the company's operating model is to external changes, such as inflation or demand fluctuations (table 1).

Table 1

Impact of economic factors on EBITDA [3, 4]

The economic factor	Impact on EBITDA	Description of the adaptation
Inflation	Increases operating costs and reduces profitability	Rising prices for raw materials, transportation and labor increase the cost of production. If the company cannot compensate for costs by raising prices for goods or services, EBITDA decreases. Companies in capital-intensive industries such as manufacturing and construction are forced to review pricing strategies or increase OE in order to maintain EBITDA.
Changing demand	Affects income and profitability from core business	In an economic downturn, consumers are cutting costs, which reduces demand for goods and services. This leads to a drop in operating income and a decrease in EBITDA. With increasing demand, companies can increase operating income, which improves the indicator. Organizations with flexible production capacities and efficient inventory management are better able to adapt to changes in demand by maintaining high EBITDA levels.
Availability of loans	Identifies opportunities for financing and expansion of operational activities	Easy access to loans allows companies to finance operational and investment needs, increase production capacity and enter new markets, which improves EBITDA. However, with difficult access to loans or rising interest rates, companies may limit investments, which reduces the level of this indicator.

Thus, this metric reveals how well companies manage to control costs and maintain profitability. Companies with a stable EBITDA level are generally more resilient to risks associated with rising operating expenses, as they can maintain sufficient profit levels to cover these costs.

Features of using EBITDA in economic instability

In conditions of economic instability caused by crises, inflation and other external factors, EBITDA becomes the most important tool for analyzing the company's sustainability. It reflects the core profitability of the business, excluding the impact of taxes, depreciation and capital structure, which allows you to **focus on the company's ability to generate operating income regardless of external factors**. In unstable conditions, companies with stable indicators can withstand fluctuations in demand and increased costs for raw materials and transportation services. For example, **Procter & Gamble** demonstrates stable EBITDA despite inflationary pressures on raw materials and logistics costs. The company compensates for rising costs by raising prices and improving production performance, which helps maintain profitability in difficult economic conditions. Such a stable indicator indicates that a business can adapt to economic shocks and control operating costs [5].

Indicator EBITDA also **helps identify companies with flexible operating models** that can quickly adapt to changing conditions. For example, **McDonald's** demonstrated an increase in this indicator during the COVID-19 crisis due to the rapid expansion of the delivery network and mobile orders [6]. Despite economic difficulties and restaurant closures, the company has successfully implemented cost reduction and process optimization measures, which allowed it to increase operating profit. Thus, companies with high EBITDA have sufficient resources to maintain their operations and demonstrate a high level of operational sustainability, despite external challenges.

Comparing the company's EBITDA with similar indicators or industry averages allows you to **understand how effectively the company conducts its operations compared to competitors**. In times of economic instability, such comparisons become especially relevant because they help identify companies that are better adapted to changes. For example, in the retail sector, most companies showed a decrease in EBITDA due to inflation and rising logistics costs. However, **Costco** managed to maintain stable performance due to the high efficiency of the supply chain and lower operating costs, which provided it with a competitive advantage [7]. The higher level of this indicator compared to the industry average indicates the company's ability to effectively manage costs and maintain operating profit in difficult conditions.

Analyzing EBITDA against industry standards **allows for consideration of the specific capital intensity and cost structure of each sector**. For example, in the energy sector, where depreciation charges account for a significant part of costs, companies can be objectively compared based on this indicator, since it excludes the impact of depreciation, which varies depending on the structure of the company's assets. This indicator is important for assessing the risks associated with financing or investments, as it allows investors and creditors to determine the company's ability to generate sufficient cash flow to service debt and meet operational obligations. Companies with high debt ratios are considered less risky because they have more opportunities to maintain stable debt payments even in conditions of economic instability, such as **Apple** [8]. In conditions where companies seek additional financing or raise capital, a stable and high EBITDA metric serves as a positive signal for investors, indicating the company's ability to handle economic challenges. Creditors and investors relying on this metric can make better-informed decisions about funding since it demonstrates the company's ability to generate income from core operations.

Indicator EBITDA is also used to **assess the potential of an investment project**. For example, if a company demonstrates stable growth, this may indicate an attractive investment prospect, since it assumes that the company is likely to fulfill debt obligations and re-invest funds in development. In conditions of economic instability, companies with high EBITDA tend to be safer investment targets because they have financial flexibility and the ability to withstand crises. Thus, this indicator in conditions of economic instability becomes an important tool for assessing the sustainability and adaptability of a business.

Conclusion

Indicator EBITDA is an important and reliable tool for assessing a business's OE, especially in conditions of economic instability. This metric focuses on a company's ability to generate profit from core activities, excluding the influence of taxes, depreciation, and debt load. Companies with high and stable EBITDA levels demonstrate the ability to control operating expenses and adapt to changing economic conditions, making them less vulnerable to external shocks. Examples of such companies, like Apple and Procter & Gamble, show how effective cost management allows for maintaining stability in this metric even under external pressures such as inflation and logistical issues.

In times of crisis, EBITDA is also used for comparative analysis and risk assessment, helping investors identify companies with sustainable operating models. Its stable level in relation to the debt burden is a positive signal for investors and creditors, as it demonstrates the financial flexibility of the company. Thus, this indicator serves not only as an indicator of operational sustainability, but also as a tool for making informed investment decisions.

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